

COMPUTATIONAL SIMULATION STUDIES TO INCREASE THE BANDWIDTH OF A DIELECTRIC RESONATOR.

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Abstract – In this work we study a technique to increase the bandwidth of dielectric resonators antennas, using computational simulation. The objective is to compare the bandwidth values of an antenna studied with a new technique with that of a traditional (cylindrical) resonator, analyzing how new geometries allow obtaining higher bandwidths.

Palavras-chave: DRAs; Simulação de antenas; HFSS; Geometria em DRAS; Largura de Banda;

INTRODUÇÃO

Antennas are referred to as a component between the transmitter and free space. [1] [2] A DRA (Dielectric Resonator Antenna) is a type of antenna that uses a dielectric material to transmit or receive electromagnetic waves. (see figure 1). Given the evolution in telecommunications, DRAs require improvements to adapt to the necessary applications. [3] In this work, currently in progress, we study a different geometry intended to verify by computer simulation an increase in bandwidth.[4]

Figura 1 – DRA simples com formato cilíndrico

DEVELOPMENT

Two samples of DRAs with excitation by a lateral probe were worked on in this article. Initially, for comparison purposes, a simple sample was simulated (a solid cylinder, traditional geometry). In the second case, the chosen geometry consisted of two samples placed side by side, one in relation to the other. The cylinders are hollowed out concentrically. The probe (excitation probe) is placed on the line joining the center of the two ceramic structures. (see figure 2)

Figura 2 – DRA dupla com formato cilíndrico vazadas no centro.

The simulation results showed a broadening of the band. The simulations were performed with the ANSYS High-Frequency Structure Simulator (HFSS) software, using the finite element method. With the help of this software, it became feasible to perform simulations and analyses of the antenna performance in any desired design. [5]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this work we present comparisons of results for two experiments (Figs 3 and 4). In the first experiment (Fig. 3) all samples have a height of 4 mm and an external radius of 7 mm. In the second experiment the height of the samples is 9 mm and also has an external radius of 7 mm. The adopted for both experiments was epsilon (ϵ_r) = 6. The tangent (tg) of losses was 0.001 for all

cases.

Figura 3 – ambas as antenas com 4mm de altura

Figura 4 – ambas as antenas com 9mm de altura.

The results found were as follows: a) for a height of 4mm, the single DRA (only one solid cylinder) obtained a bandwidth of 2.915GHz, while for a double DRA of the same height (4mm) 5.030GHz was obtained. In the simulation with heights of 9mm, it was found that the single DRA (one cylinder) presented 1.290GHz, while using the double DRA of the same height (9mm) a bandwidth of 3.684GHz was obtained. We therefore conclude that the adopted strategy represents a possibility of obtaining an increase in bandwidth.

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